

Languages and Cultures of Ancient Italy. Historical Linguistics and Digital Models

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ABSTRACT

The poster presents a newly started project about languages and cultures of Ancient Italy, which brings together competences from Historical Linguistics, Computational Lexicography and Digital Humanities. The main objective of the project is to investigate the cultures of ancient Italy on the basis of their linguistic documentation (7th - 1st c. B.C.) by means of digital tools specifically tailored for their peculiarities.

KEYWORDS

Restsprachen, Ancient Italy, Epigraphic Text Corpora, Computational Lexica, Semantic Web

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

During the period dating from the appearance of writing (8th c. B.C.) until complete linguistic Romanisation (1st c. B.C. to 1st c. A.D.), ancient Italy is characterised by the presence of numerous linguistic varieties, which are both Indo-European and non-Indo-European. These varieties are documented by *corpora* that are not homogenous in their quantity, quality, geographical distribution, and chronology. Apart from this lack of homogeneity, with the exception of the Latin of Rome they can be qualified as *Restsprachen*, i.e. fragmentarily attested languages, inasmuch as their linguistic documentation consists almost exclusively of epigraphic texts, mostly short and repetitive. For this reason, *Restsprachen* often present specific problems concerning the reading of the inscriptions, the segmentation into words, their linguistic analysis, and their interpretation. The linguistic framework as *Restsprachen* of the languages involved in this project – Venetic, Oscan, Faliscan, and Celtic – thus requires the adoption of specific methods and approaches for the analysis and edition of their texts[10][17][20]. To achieve this challenging goal, we will combine the traditional method proper to Historical Linguistics and its products (study, edition, and the linguistic, historical, and cultural commentary on the texts) with the setting up of digital technologies that will facilitate scholars in their activities.

2. OBJECTIVES

The main goal of the project is to investigate the cultures of ancient Italy on the basis of the relevant linguistic documentation in order to show the forms of linguistic variability in Italy before Romanisation. The study and valorisation of this cultural heritage is to be achieved through interdisciplinary work that brings together methods and practices from the “traditional” study of such materials, computational lexicology and lexicography, semantic web and various digital humanities technology, such as digital archiving, textual corpora, contextualisation and visualisation methods. In particular, we aim at digitising key materials and deploying electronic tools and resources that will permit their easy consultation and revision, which in turn will both facilitate scholars’ work and allow greater disclosure of the acquired scientific knowledge. Given the experimental nature of the project, we will focus on the Venetic, Oscan, Faliscan, and Celtic *corpora*. Although ambitious and challenging, given the main goal of the project, i.e. to develop a new methodology that leverages specifically tailored digital technologies to facilitate scholars’ work and collaboration while at the same time ensuring long term preservation of the acquired knowledge, the risks are calculated. To minimise them we build upon our own direct experiences in developing tools for the digital humanities and in modeling language data, as well as upon other similar national and European endeavours. At the end of the project, it is expected that both the methodology as well as the digital toolkit and technology set up will be ready to be extended to the other *Restsprachen*.

3. METHODOLOGIES AND EXPECTED OUTCOMES

The project plans to create a digital set of interrelated resources: a *corpus* of epigraphic texts, a computational lexicon for the languages involved, a dataset of bibliographic references, and an experimental semantic dataset of interpretations. The *corpus* of the texts will be managed and exploited in a digital archive containing the formal representation of the texts leveraging the TEI/EpiDoc encoding schema [9]; it may be necessary to create an *ad-hoc* schema for the peculiarities presented by languages of fragmentary attestation, the EpiDoc model having been used so far only for the creation of annotated ‘major’ corpora, especially of Greek and Latin inscriptions. For example, *Restsprachen* may require the identification of standards suitable for the encoding of unusual and odd writing ductus, punctuation marks with particular values (e.g. syllabic punctuation), characters whose linguistic nature is uncertain, multiple hypotheses of word segmentation, etc. The application of the EpiDoc model to *Restsprachen* is, thus, a complete novelty in the field. Each text in the archive will be enriched with shared and standard metadata allowing for an accurate description, both as a linguistic object (text: language, alphabet, date, etc.) and as a material object (support: chronology, data of discovery, material, etc.). Accordingly, such a description will facilitate the retrieval of relevant information. The project additionally plans to experiment with the use of CRMtex[11][12] and CRMinf[4] extensions of CIDOC CRM, the *de facto* standard ontology in the Digital Humanities for the representation of the texts and their scientific interpretation in a semantic format[5]. As regards the lexicon, the project will investigate the specific requirements for the design of an efficient computational lexical model specifically dedicated to languages of fragmentary attestation in order to produce a multilingual (Venetic, Oscan, Faliscan, and Celtic) computational lexicon. We will adopt Semantic Web standards and vocabularies for providing a structured and formal representation of the lexical items and their related information as well as for allowing for a sophisticated semantic access to the *corpus* of epigraphies [1][16]. The challenges to be faced in lexical modeling are numerous, since we are dealing with *Restsprachen*, and they range from lemmatisation issues, as in many cases the relationship between words and lemmas is not certain for various reasons (different graphic standards, difficult linguistic analysis, incomplete paradigms, etc.), to sense representation, given that meanings are often only partially and hypothetically reconstructible, and smart reference or linking to attestations. Fortunately, recent efforts within modeling and standardisation initiatives are tackling many of these critical issues, and they will provide us with inspiration and guidance. We refer in particular to the works on the extension of existing representation models such as TEI and Ontolex-lemon for the account of attestations[3] and etymologies[2][14][13]. Models and methods for interlinking the datasets will also be designed as the backbone for a digital toolkit that will allow for both the creation/revision of some of the materials and their online fruition, see [15][8][19][18]. Specifically, the heart of the toolkit will be a lexicon editing and consultation service specifically tailored to *Restsprachen*, based on inhouse previous experiences[1]; this will be enriched for allowing the interlinking among the different datasets, thus acting as a sort of hub that will primarily integrate lexicon and epigraphy transcriptions, together with contextual metadata, bibliography, and experimentally the hermeneutic positions. It is also planned to experiment with Domain-Specific Languages to deploy a system that can assist scholars in the creation of the textual digital resources and ensure compatibility with the aforementioned standards[19]. The tools and resources produced and developed within the project will finally be made available through relevant European-wide Research Infrastructures such as CLARIN[6] and DARIAH[7], the two currently most relevant infrastructures for the e-Humanities and (immaterial) Cultural Heritage. This will ensure both a long-term preservation of the resources produced and a high valorisation of this heritage.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project is supported by the Italian Ministry of Research [PRIN 2017XJLE8J]

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